

Assessment of Provision and Management of Internet Services among Federal Universities in Northwest, Nigeria

*Ahmad, Sirajo Muhammad Ph.D.¹

Email: Abusuraj070@gmail.com

Tel: +2347066593180

Muhammad, Saratu Mera Ph.D.²

Email: saratu.mera@fubk.edu.ng

Tel: +23481615570

¹Sokoto State College of Basic and Remedial Education

²Federal University Birnin Kebbi, Kebbi State.

Abstract

The rapid evolution of the internet has significantly transformed higher education globally. Nigerian universities, like many institutions worldwide, are embracing the digital age by providing internet services to enhance learning, research, and administrative operations. This paper assessed the provision and management of internet services among Federal Universities in North-west, Nigeria. The study adopted descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consisted of 19120 (42 management staff, 6447 teaching staff, 12344 non-teaching staff and 287 students' representatives) from all the Federal Universities in North-west, Nigeria. The sample size for the study was 557 stakeholders (comprising 129 teaching staff, 248 non-teaching staff, 152 students' representatives and 28 management staff). Hence, this was arrived at using multi-stage sampling technique within all the states in North-west, Nigeria. A closed ended questionnaire adapted from Maina (2016) titled "Assessment of the Provision and Management of Students Internet Services Questionnaire" was used for data collection. The descriptive statistics of frequency count and percentages were used for the analysis of the research question and decision mean of 3.0 was used to determine acceptance or rejection of the item statement as structured in the instrument to answer the research questions. Inferential statistics of Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. Findings from the study revealed that although internet service is provided and managed in Federal Universities in North-west, Nigeria, but there were issues of lack of adequate maintenance of the internet facilities. It was concluded that internet services in Federal Universities are poorly managed. Therefore, the study recommended among others that more effort should be geared towards ensuring that there are adequate measures put in place for regular maintenance of existing internet facilities among Federal Universities in North-west, Nigeria.

Keywords: Internet services, Management, Stakeholders, Provision.

Introduction

The internet has revolutionized education, offering vast resources and collaborative opportunities that enhance teaching, learning, and research in higher institutions globally. Nigerian universities have recognized the importance of internet access in advancing education and are making efforts to provide reliable connectivity. Indeed, the Internet is an inseparable part of today's educational system. The academic community increasingly depends on the Internet for educational purposes; University students are increasingly using the Internet as an information resource while in search of information for academic assignments, playing online games, streaming videos, online shopping and such others. Thus, the emergence of the Internet has had a profound impact on society in general and on library and information services in particular (Allison, 2016). Majority of academic and research institutions provide and manage Internet service for staff and students to enhance teaching and learning. Students also use the Internet for social communication which helps them expand and build new relationships. Allison (2016) reported that, students use the Internet more than 5 hours per day, more than 25% of those are in their 20's, and they rather browse the Internet on their smartphones, than on laptops or school property computers. Students utilize the Internet to speak with lecturers and colleagues, for research and to get access to library resource. Therefore, Internet serves as a useful tool in support of the various educational activities that ranged from research to teaching. Affum (2022) opined that internet help students to access journals and articles which otherwise are not made available in the libraries. The author remarked further that, increase in internet use was very useful in the improvement of students learning outcome. Similarly, Jackson, (2011) cited

Assessment of Provision and Manag ...(Ahmad & Muhammad, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10408154>

in Ahmad (2022) also noted that, the Internet will level the educational playing field due to its availability to everyone, everywhere, and any time irrespective of gender, race/ethnicity, income or other socio-demographic characteristics. In the same line of thinking Siraj (2015) opined that internet enhances easy communication in the academic community. Thus, the Internet is a vital tool that will propel university education to greater heights as the world move further into the knowledge-based economy.

Universities worldwide now invest a lot on internet access because it reduces the time between the production and utilization of knowledge; improves co-operation and exchange of ideas with fellow researchers in other institutions, regions or countries, furthers the sharing of information; and promotes multidisciplinary research. Oso and Adesina (2017) highlighting the importance of internet services stated that having access to internet allows students to keep up with information that might not make it into textbooks or might be outdated by the time it is published in a traditional format. The internet provide easy access to information and help students to do their assignments with just only search on the search engine and also give them the opportunity to exchange ideas and information from different locations at the same time (Affum 2022). Thus, survival in academics without the Internet can be very difficult. The Internet harbors applications used in online data repositories, library catalogues, journals, news services, student and financial administration systems, online supported or solely online conducted teaching, as well as in digital communication with fellow students' and lecturers. Other contemporary uses of Internet by students include purchasing, entertainment, and even dating. Consequently, studies have been carried out in many places to understand how University students' and staff use the Internet, the purposes for which the students' and staff use the Internet, the search engines used, their internet skills as well as problems that hinder efficient internet use among others. Chan and Fu (2015) observed that the internet is very useful to university students' and staff in Nigeria because it enables them to have access to timely, accurate and relevant information that cannot be obtained from library shelves. The authors remarked further that, Internet searching helps University students to boost their intellectual development and job preparation. Hence, due to the endless nature of information resources on the Internet, libraries are increasingly investing in provision of Internet services and resources to enable their clients have better access to the information. However, Aguolu (2012) in Ahmad (2022) asserts that resources may be available in the library and sometimes there may be identified bibliography relevant to one's area of interest, but the user may not be able to locate the material. Constraints to effective utilization of internet have been identified by researchers in varying degrees (Omotayo, 2016; Siraj 2015; Bassey 2019; Affum, 2022). In relation to the internet access challenges, Omotayo (2016) found that the major barriers to efficient Internet use by students include slowness of the server and payment for the access time. Similarly, Bassey (2019) reported that were not easily accessible to students due to malfunctioning of some facilities, irregular power supply and the negligence of the management in subscribing to the internet services. Luambo and Nawe (2014) also observe that the slow Internet connections attributable to small bandwidth is a major factor hindering Internet access and use in Africa.

Indeed, the mode of acquiring and disseminating information for university education has changed from just physically available prints to a combination of physical and e-materials with virtual reality. As a result of that Akintunde (2012) in Ahmad (2022) opined that, any attempt to have meaningful academic communication can be successful only by the use of ICT which presents information in real time and space. Youngsters especially students' and researchers spend most of their time in cybercafé because the service is not adequately available in the university community, they risk travelling a further distance to transact one business or another on the internet. These members of the university community use the Internet for the resources it provides. Internet services according to Ikoro (2012) in Ahmad (2022), include e-mailing, world wide web browsing, telephoning, and telex/video conferencing and others. Available also in the internet are social media resource such as audio broadcasting, news and discussion/chart group, face-book YouTube and twitter resources. In relation using those resources available on the internet Cisse (2014) noted that students' and researchers are disposed to access maximum information and communicate at world level. Thus, they can debate democratically and freely while being exposed to happenings in their fields of activities as well as other subjects. Chifwepa (2013) discovered a high use of internet by the staff of the University of Zambia where 35 out of 37 staff made use of internet. Their major motivation for such use was convenience (82.91%); usefulness (80.05%); free access to information and software (71.4%); and ease of use (68.6%). In Nigeria, findings from the study of Oso and Adesina (2017) indicated that the government provides internet services in the institution but teachers and student cannot regularly access the services due to negligence of the school management in terms of regular subscription to the internet services, lack of upgrade and maintenance of the available facilities. While Jagdoro (2014) in his own research ascertained that 45.2% of graduate students access the Internet at the cybercafé in the university where only 8.2% used the library Internet facilities. A greater percentage (38.24%) did that only on monthly basis where 39.7% spent one hour on each visit.

Assessment of Provision and Manag ...(Ahmad & Muhammad, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10408154>

From the above assertions it appears that although internet services play a significant role in facilitating access to information and dissemination of information, something is lacking in the quality and quantity of such services in Nigerian Public universities. Therefore, it is against the background of that the researchers conducted an assessment on provision and management of internet services among Federal Universities in North-west, Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The objective of the study was to:

To access the extent of provision and management of internet services among Federal Universities in North-west, Nigeria

Research Question

The following research question guided the study:

What is the extent of provision and management of internet services among Federal Universities in North-west, Nigeria

Hypothesis

The following research hypothesis was raised to guide the study:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the extent of provision and management of internet services among federal Universities in North-west, Nigeria.

Methodology

The researchers adopted descriptive survey research design for the study. The population of the study was 19120, (which comprised 42 management staffs, 6447 teaching staff, 12344 non-teaching staff and 287 students' representatives) in all the Federal Universities in North-west, Nigeria. The sample size for the study was 557 (comprising 129 teaching staff, 248 non-teaching staff, 152 students' representatives and 28 management staff). The sample was derived from Research Advisor (2006). A closed ended questionnaire adapted from Maina (2016) was used to generate the relevant data for the study. Questionnaire was titled "Assessment of Provision and Management of Internet Services Questionnaire (APMISQ). A 5-point Likert scale was used such as Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD) Undecided (U). The reliability of the Questionnaire was established through pilot test using test re-test method. Result from the two tests were subjected to Pearson Product Moment Correlation test in order to determine the reliability Coefficient of the study, a reliability coefficient of 0.68 was obtained at 0.05 level of significance. The instrument was therefore declared reliable. Collection of data was done by the researchers with the help of research assistants. The description statistics: frequency count and percentages were used for bio-data of the respondents and decision mean of 3.0 was used to determine acceptance or rejection of the item statement as structured in the instrument to answer the research questions. Inferential statistics of Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance.

Result

Research Question

What is the extent of provision and management of internet services among Federal Universities in North-west, Nigeria.

Assessment of Provision and Manag ... (Ahmad & Muhammad, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10408154>

Table 1: Mean Scores of Respondents on Provision and Management of Internet Services in Federal Universities of Northwest Geographical Zone, Nigeria.

S/N	Item statement	Category of Respondent	Strongly Agreed	Agreed	Undecided	Disagreed	Strongly Disagreed	Number	Mean
1	There is Internet service in the University	Management staff	22	5	1	22	-	49	3.6
		Teaching staff	13	90	8	-	-	110	4.0
		Non-teaching. staff	17	80	3	-	14	108	3.9
		Students	82	10	-	7	-	107	4.3
2	The internet service works every day for the benefit of students	Management staff	12	19	-	8	10	49	3.3
		Teaching staff	21	80	-	5	5	110	4.0
		Non-teaching. staff	53	15	2	37	7	108	3.8
		Students	50	37	-	12	8	107	4.0
3	The university internet is used for research by students to improve their academic achievement.	Management staff	20	10	-	8	11	49	3.4
		Teaching staff	60	41	4	6	-	110	4.4
		Non-teaching. staff	58	27	7	12	8	108	4.1
		Students	56	34	4	9	4	107	4.2
4	University makes provision for free wireless in the campus	Management staff	13	22	-	12	3	49	3.6
		Teaching staff	60	10	7	30	4	110	3.8
		Non-teaching. staff	62	30	-	20	2	108	4.3
		Students	65	17	-	22	2	107	4.1
5	University provides modem to students to enable them get access to the Internet service.	Management staff	6	3	1	37	2	49	2.6
		Teaching staff	5	20	11	73	2	110	2.5
		Non-teaching. staff	10	30	-	70	4	108	2.2
		Students	28	5	-	54	10	107	2.3
6	The University internet is easily accessible.	Management staff	20	8	-	10	11	49	3.3
		Teaching staff	54	-	1	25	30	110	3.2
		Non-teaching. staff	55	32	-	27	-	108	4.2
		Students	85	6	-	9	7	107	4.4
7	The University is linked to internet service	Management staff	6	10	4	10	19	49	2.4
		Teaching staff	100	10	-	31	20	110	4.5
		Non-teaching. staff	43	2	-	13	4	108	2.3
		Students	66	7	-	34	10	107	4.0
8	Students are patronizing e-library for their research.	Management staff	16	10	1	13	9	49	3.2
		Teaching staff	39	50	-	6	17	110	3.8
		Non-teaching. staff	61	27	-	9	7	108	4.0
		Students	84	6	-	12	5	107	4.4
9	The internet service is well managed	Management staff	14	28	-	4	3	49	3.9
		Teaching staff	28	58	5	5	15	110	3.7
		Non-teaching. staff	51	30	-	23	-	108	3.8
		Students	87	10	-	8	2	107	4.5
10	The management supervises the internet facilities regularly	Management staff	10	20	-	17	2	49	3.3
		Teaching staff	15	63	5	19	9	110	3.5
		Non-tech. staff	61	3	6	40	3	108	3.8
		Students	44	45	-	16	2	107	4.0
11	Spoiled facilities are replaced promptly	Management staff	12	19	-	8	10	49	3.3
		Teaching staff	21	50	-	20	20	110	3.3
		Non-teaching. staff	40	10	2	55	7	108	3.3
		Students	57	30	-	12	8	107	4.0
12	The computers in the E-Library are well maintained	Management staff	20	10	-	19	-	49	3.6
		Teaching staff	60	31	4	6	10	110	4.1
		Non-teaching. staff	40	27	7	30	8	108	3.6
		Students	46	44	4	9	4	107	4.1

Source: Fieldwork, 2022

Assessment of Provision and Manag ...(Ahmad & Muhammad, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10408154>

Table 1 revealed the views of Management staff, Teaching staff, non-teaching staff and Students on provision and management of internet services in Federal Universities of North-west zone. Item 1 revealed opinions of the respondents on Whether there is Internet services in the University. From the responses of the respondents, the item statement was accepted by the respondents with the mean scores of 3.6, 4.0, 3.9 and 4.3 respectively. Item 2 showed the views of respondents on whether the internet service works every day for the benefit of students. The mean scores of the respondents showed that the item was accepted by the respondents with the mean scores of 3.3, 4.0, 3.8, and 4.0 for Management staff, teaching staff, non-teaching staff and Students respectively. Item 3 was on whether the University internet is used for research by students to improve their academic achievement. The opinions of the respondents showed that the item statement was accepted that is Management staff had a mean score of 3.4, Teaching staff 4.4, non-teaching staff had 4.1 and Students had 4.2. Item 4 was on whether University makes provision for free wireless in the campus. The mean scores of 3.6, 3.8, 4.3 and 4.1 were obtained from the responses of the respondents, implying that the respondents accepted the item statement. Item 5 is on whether University makes provision for free wireless in the campus. The item was also accepted by the respondents with the mean scores of 3.6, 4.5, 4.2 and 3.0 for Management staff, Teaching staff, non-teaching staff and Students. Similarly, item 6 was accepted by the respondents with the mean scores of 3.3, 3.2, 4.2 and 4.2 for Management staff, Teaching staff, non-teaching staff and Students respectively. Item 7 was to find out whether the University is linked to internet service. The mean score showed that the item was accepted by all the categories of the respondents with the decision means of 3.3, 3.3, 3.9 and 3.2 for Management staff, Teaching staff, non-teaching staff and Students respectively. Item 8 was on whether Students are patronizing e-library for their research. The item statement was accepted by the respondents with the mean scores of 3.2, 3.8, 4.0 and 4.4 respectively. From item 9, the decision mean of the respondents were found to be 3.9, 3.7, 3.8 and 4.5, meaning the item was accepted by the respondents. Item 10 was on whether the management supervises the internet facilities regularly, the Item was accepted by all the respondents with the mean scores of 3.6, 4.0, 4.2 and 3.7 respectively. Item 11 was on whether spoiled facilities are replaced promptly. The item was accepted by all the respondents with the mean scores of 3.3, 3.5, and 4.0 respectively. Item 12 was on whether the computers in the E-Library are well maintained. The item was accepted by the respondents with the mean scores of 3.6, 4.1, 3.6 and 4.1, respectively. From the analysis of Table 1, it was established that internet services are provided in most of the Federal Universities of Northwest Geographical Zone, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Testing

H01: There was no significant difference between the extent of provision and management of internet services among Federal Universities in North-west, Nigeria.

Table 2: Summary of the One Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on the extent of Provision and Management of Internet Services among Federal Universities in North-west, Nigeria.

Dialogue	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	9.558	3	3.186	2.211	0.085
Within Groups	496.960	372	1.373		
Total	506.518	374			

Source: Fieldwork, 2022

From table 2, the F-value is 2.311 and the P-value is 0.085 at 0.05 level of significance. Since the P-value is greater than the level of significance set for the study, the hypothesis is therefore retained. Thus, there is no significant difference in the opinions of respondents on Perception of Stakeholders (respondents) on Provision and Management of Internet services in universities of northwest geographical zone, Nigeria. This means Internet services were provided in the Federal Universities of North-west zone, but there were issues of inadequate maintenance of the facilities.

Discussion of Findings

It was revealed by the findings of this study that Internet services are provided in most of the Federal Universities in North-west, Nigeria, but there are issues of inadequate maintenance of the facilities in the Federal Universities. This was revealed from the responses of the respondents to the structured questions given to them. The result from the analysis shows that there was a unanimous acceptance of all the item statements on the research question which indicated that Internet services

Assessment of Provision and Manag ...(Ahmad & Muhammad, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10408154>

are provided in most of the Federal Universities, findings also showed that there is inadequate maintenance of those facilities; responses from the participants shows among others that, there is Internet service in the Universities; The internet service works every day for the benefit of students; The Universities internet is used for research by students to improve their academic achievement; Universities makes provision for free wireless in the campus. The findings are in support of the findings of Chifwepa (2013) who discovered a high use of internet by the staff of the University of Zambia and their major motivation for such use was convenience (82.91%); usefulness (80.05%); free access to information and software (71.4%); and ease of use (68.6%). In Nigeria Jagdoro (2014), in his own research also, ascertained that 45.2% of graduate students access the Internet at the cybercafé in the university where only 8.2% used the library Internet facilities. A greater percentage (38.24%) did that only on monthly basis where 39.7% spent one hour on each visit. The outcome of this study also support the findings from the study of Oso and Adesina (2017) which indicated that, the government provides internet services in the institution but teachers and student cannot regularly access the services due to negligence of the school management in terms of regular subscription to the internet services, lack of upgrade and maintenance of the available facilities This finding has highlighted the fact that although internet services are provided in universities, lack of proper and regular maintenance is affecting the ability of students and staff to optimally utilize such services.

Conclusion

The paper concluded that, although, internet services are provided in most of the Federal Universities in North-west, Nigeria, but there are issues of inadequate maintenance of the facilities despite the prospects provision and management of internet services in Nigerian universities hold for transforming education, research, and administrative operations. Thus, challenges related to provision and management of the internet service must be addressed collaboratively by universities management, government, and all other stakeholders through strategic interventions and concerted efforts, in order to harness the full potential of the internet for the betterment of education and society at large.

Recommendations

1. The University management should increase access to Internet services in Federal Universities to meet both students and staff demand.
2. The University management should ensure that there are adequate measures put in place for regular maintenance of existing internet facilities in Federal Universities in North-west zone, Nigeria.

Acknowledgements

Our sincere gratitude go to the Almighty Allah for making it possible for us to undertake this daunting task. Our profound appreciation goes to all the scholars whose work we have consulted. Indeed, your valuable contributions have helped refined the work to an acceptable standard. To the participants of this study, we cannot thank you enough for your tremendous support and cooperation throughout the process of data collection. We also appreciate our colleagues for their words of encouragement. To our mentors who are too numerous to be mentioned, we appreciate your continuous support and encouragement towards academic excellence. Lastly, we say a big thank you to our families for their support and encouragement.

Reference

- Affum, M.Q. (2022). The effect of internet on students' studies: a review. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. e-journal) 6932. <http://digitalcommons.unl.edu/l.bphilprac/6932>
- Agnola I. (2012). An investigation in the state of health in secondary school of Borabu Division in Nyarira District. Unpublished P.G.D.E Research Project. Kenyatta University.
- Ahmad, S. (2022). Stakeholders' perception on provision and management of internet services in Federal Universities of North-west Zone, Nigeria. Unpublished Ph.D. Thesis. Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Kaduna State.
- Allison, D.P. (2016). *Hand Book on extracurricular activities*. Jos- Elindero Nig. Ltd.
- Bassey, A. (2019). Availability, Accessibility and competency of students in the use of internet services: a case study of educational technology unit of Federal College of Education Obudu, Cross Rivers State, Nigeria. Retrieved from Open Library.distance.edu
- Chan, J.K and Fu, Y.T. (2015) Improvement on student feeding in Nairobi, Kenya. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net>.

Assessment of Provision and Manag ...(Ahmad & Muhammad, 2023) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10408154>

- Chiwepa (2013). *Some aspect of university management*. Lagos-Educational Industries Limited.
- Cisse, I.M. (2014) An investigation in to the provision and management of student welfare and social services. (unpublished thesis). University of Benin, Edo state Nigeria.
- Elliot, S.B. (2014) Influence of internet usage on academic performance and face to face communication. *Journal of psychology and Behavioral Sciences*, 2(2): 163-186.
- Jagdor P. (2014). *Appraisal technique in internet service*. Jos- University press
- John. R.O. (2012). *Fundamental principles of teaching guidance & counselling in high institutions (2nd ed)*. Retrieved from <https://www.cochranlibrary.com>
- Lumbago I. and Nare L. (2014). Problem and prospect of student welfare services in Nairobi, kenya. Retrieved from <https://www.cochranlibrary.com>
- Omotayo, M. N. (2016). *Primary responsibilities of food managers*. Lagos-educational Industries limited Nigeria.
- Oso, S.O. and Adesina, V.O. (2017). Availability, utilization of facilities among undergraduate students of Colleges of Education in Nigeria. *European Centre for Research, Training and Development. Rol,5(9): 100-107*
- Siraj, H.H. (2015). Internet use and academic performance of students in Indonesian public University. *International Medical Journal*, 22(2):83-86.